

The Role of Phraseology in Foreign Language Learning: A Case Study of French Phraseological Derivatives

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Abstract: *Phraseology is one of the modern branches of linguistics and is a very important direction in the study of a foreign language, since it reveals the richness and uniqueness of the language. This article examines the methods by which phraseological derivatives are formed in the French language and considers the contributions of linguists who have conducted research in this area.*

Keywords: *phraseological units, derivatives, semantic and lexical aspects, syntactic structure, metonymic expansion.*

Phraseology plays a significant role in language learning, as it unveils the richness and uniqueness of a language. Phraseological units, frequently used to convey specific meanings, are subject to the process of phraseological derivation—the formation of new fixed expressions. This article examines the methods by which phraseological derivatives are formed in the French language and considers the contributions of linguists who have conducted research in this area.

Several notable scholars have studied phraseological derivation and made significant contributions to this field:

V. N. Teliya: Known for her research on the semantics and structure of phraseological units and their cultural implications.

A. V. Kunin: A foundational figure in phraseology as a linguistic discipline, he introduced the concept of "phraseological derivation" and studied the mechanisms through which new idioms are created.

E. N. Amosova: Focused on the phraseological connections that enriched phraseology theory, especially regarding derivation.

N. M. Shansky: Studied both lexical and phraseological derivation, with attention to the structure and meaning of idiomatic expressions.

V. P. Zhukov: Investigated phraseological derivation through the lens of lexical nomination and the role of idioms in developing new meanings.

Among these, Alexander Vasilievich Kunin made a substantial contribution to phraseology by being one of the first researchers to systematically study phraseological derivation. His notable works include:

1. *"English Phraseology: A Theoretical Course"* (1970): This seminal work lays the foundation for phraseology theory, discussing idiom formation and analyzing phraseological derivation in English.
2. *"A Course of Modern English Phraseology"* (1986): Here, Kunin expands his research, exploring derivation and analyzing the creation of new phraseological structures.

3. Various articles on phraseological derivation: Kunin's detailed examination of phraseological nomination, derivation, and structural and semantic shifts in idioms was published in several scholarly journals, including *Questions of Linguistics*.
4. "*Phraseology of Modern English*" (1956): As one of the first in-depth studies on phraseology, this work defines the basis of phraseological derivation and discusses the formation and transformation of idiomatic expressions in language.

Kunin's research laid the groundwork for phraseology as a discipline and significantly influenced subsequent studies on phraseological derivation, especially within comparative analyses of English and Russian. In France, researchers such as Raymond Williams, Jean Dubois, and Claude Hagège have also contributed to phraseological studies. They analyzed the wealth of language and examined the semantic and lexical aspects of phraseological units. For example, Raymond Williams explored the new meanings generated through the combination of words and expressions. Jean Dubois conducted in-depth research on the morphological and syntactic structures of phraseological units, while Claude Hagège studied historical and cultural transformations within idioms.

Methods of Forming Phraseological Derivatives. In the French language, phraseological derivatives are formed through several methods:

1. **Metaphorical Expansion:** Idioms are often created through metaphorical use. For instance, the expression "*avoir le cœur sur la main*" (literally "to have one's heart on one's hand," meaning "to be generous") employs its base meaning to describe someone who is always willing to help.
2. **Metonymic Expansion:** Metonymy is also widely employed in the creation of idioms. For example, the phrase "*prendre la mouche*" (literally "to catch a fly," meaning "to get offended quickly") acquired a new emotional connotation through metonymic expansion.
3. **Syntactic Modification:** New meanings can emerge by altering the syntactic structure of idioms. The expression "*tirer les ficelles*" (literally "to pull the strings," meaning "to manipulate someone") is now more commonly used to signify manipulation.
4. **Enrichment with Additional Elements:** New words or elements can be added to idioms, creating new meanings. For example, the expression "*faire d'une pierre deux coups*" (literally "to kill two birds with one stone") is sometimes enriched with additional adjectives, adding semantic complexity to the idiom.

Analysis of Examples. Phraseological derivatives have particular significance in linguistics, as they reflect cultural and historical processes. For instance, the phrase "*mettre les bâtons dans les roues*" (literally "to put sticks in the wheels," meaning "to hinder someone") originally related to manual labor but now broadly signifies creating obstacles for any action or project. The idiom "*appeler un chat un chat*" (literally "to call a cat a cat") emphasizes straightforward and honest communication. Linguistic analysis of this phraseological unit shows its evolution toward the meaning of speaking truthfully without embellishment.

In conclusion, French phraseological derivatives are formed through multiple methods, revealing the language's richness and uniqueness. The research conducted by scholars such as Raymond Williams, Jean Dubois, and Claude Hagège deepens our understanding of the formation and evolution of idioms. Idiomatic expressions expand through metaphor, metonymy, syntactic modifications, and the addition of new elements, which enriches and complicates the language. As phraseological research progresses, new methods of forming phraseological derivatives are expected to emerge. Continued exploration of this area and study of various aspects of phraseology are therefore essential.

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